

There is a day time twin paradox that involves the language time travelling clock, the linguistics time travelling clock, the pronunciation time travelling clock, and the dynasty time travelling clock, and it goes as followed:

- If paired language time travelling clock with linguistics time travelling clock, then pronunciation time travelling clock, however, if pronunciation time travelling clock, then dynasty time travelling clock, however, if dynasty time travelling clock, then paired language time travelling clock with linguistics time travelling clock.

In this day time twin paradox explained and shown above, the language time travelling clock and the linguistics time travelling clock are paired with each other, the pronunciation time travelling clock is the extra, and the dynasty time travelling clock is the outcome of that time twin paradox, where the name for this time twin paradox is the magic day time twin paradox.

This set is timed as 8:46, and is dated as the 9th day of the 2nd month, of the 2025th year.